

A Poem by Rajendra Nath Dutta

Scythe and Spade

Shah Jahan built the Taj Mahal,
The ivory-white marble mausoleum -
The jewel of Mughal art.
I do disagree; I oppose,
I am a sculptor.

King Nebuchadnezzar of
Mesopotamia
Built the Hanging Gardens of Babylon;
Wonder of wonders of the ancient world.
I hardly comply; I react,
I am a labourer.

Pharaoh Cheops built the Great Pyramid at Giza,
A testament to the advanced engineering and astronomical Knowhow.
Hardly does it appease me: I dissent all dictators.
I am a proletariat.

Did they build?
Or Did I build them in aggregate?
I record the chronicle of the scythe and spade.
I de-structure the archetypal societal pattern ---
A class, elite to order and own
And the other only to obey, oblige and ooze.

Bio:

Rajendra Nath Dutta is presently serving as Associate Professor of English, Midnapore College (Autonomous), Midnapore, West Bengal, India. Born in Odisha and serving in West Bengal for last thirty four years, he has shown wide interest in translating Bengali poems to Odiya and English in many volumes of the trilingual "The Trimatrik", published by The Upatyaka. He has published a Collection of Poems in Odiya "Salitatro Abhilasha" and a Collection of Poems in English "Crest and Trough". He is now engaged in translating selected Rabindra Sangeet for his next publication.

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